

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN ASTRONOMY TEACHING AND ITS PRACTICAL ESSENCE

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Abstract. *Over the past few decades, interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary studies have become a major factor in the development of science. The most important discoveries are observed in several areas of astronomy. Astronomy it is important that mathematics, physics, physical chemistry, biophysics, biochemistry, geophysics and other sciences are related to teaching based on an integrative approach.*

Keywords: *interdisciplinary sciences, multidisciplinary sciences, astronomy, mathematics, physics, physical chemistry, biophysics, biochemistry, geophysics.*

Today, special attention is being paid to the education system, as well as to all areas. We observe that a number of reforms are being implemented in higher education, which is an integral part of continuous education. In this regard, the implementation of the tasks provided for in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5032 of March 29, 2021 "On measures to increase the quality of education in the field of physics and develop scientific research" is of great importance. In the teaching of astronomy on the basis of interdisciplinary integration, importance is attached to the development ability and cognitive potential of the individual.

At the world level, research efforts aimed at improving the effectiveness of teaching of concrete, natural and technical sciences, in particular, physics, its youngest and fastest growing field, astronomy, i.e. invisible and imagination-based processes, are being conducted intensively. Wide use of modern information and pedagogical technologies, the principle of interdisciplinary, and various methods and approaches that serve to increase the efficiency of mastering are widely used. In particular, Crocodile, which occupies a large place in the world Internet network. Som., Yenka.com., Physics and other sites and the software installed on them can also be cited as examples. These software tools and various methods are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of teaching astronomy. The reforms in the field of education in our country require the training of mature and high-level thinking personnel for the development of society. This requires raising both content and style of teaching to a higher level. This demand for continuous education system is reflected in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training", reports of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of education.

The role of mathematical operations in the dynamic development of integration from the beginning to the end of training in astronomy is incomparable. If it is desirable to study the planets in the solar system at the beginning, then it is necessary to synthesize scattered knowledge and skills, and then at the end of the training to derive the parameters of the planets through mathematical operations, that is, this is a narrow specialty, but expressed at a new integration level. Integration as a teaching tool is aimed at developing the student's erudition, updating the existing narrow specialization in teaching. At the same time, it clearly explains that integration should not

replace the teaching of classical academic subjects, but should only integrate the acquired knowledge into a single system.

Analyzing the literature of astronomy, it is possible to observe the definition of integration: integration is the ability of the topics and subjects of the scientific disciplines of astronomy to have ideas and potential, deepen, develop and multiply their interrelationship. edged. the natural interrelationship of the studied processes and phenomena. For this, it is necessary to study as a single subject, rather than combining different parts.

By studying the features of the current stage of development of astronomy, we have distinguished the current tendencies:

By using an integrative approach in education based on scientific research: development of an electronic information-educational resource based on integrated approaches (coherence, synectics, introjection) in the formation of basic and subject-related special competencies in students; creation of informational and methodical support for the formation of special competences in students based on an integrative approach; development of a methodology for the organization of virtual laboratories in the science of history on the basis of person-oriented education; it is possible to contribute to the effectiveness of education as a result of the development of methodical recommendations that serve to form the special competencies of students in the electronic educational environment.

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